

INDIRECT TRANSLATION RECONSIDERED: ETHICS, HISTORY, AND THE CHANGING CONCEPTION OF TRANSLATION

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Indirect translation, understood as the practice of translating a text through a third language (Pięta, Maia and Torres-Simón 2023), has existed since the earliest periods of translation history. Yet attitudes toward this practice have varied considerably over time, reflecting changing conceptions of translation, authorship, and ethics. This keynote explores how indirect translation can serve as a lens through which to observe the historical development of translation ethics and the evolving understanding of what translation is, two areas that are ultimately interconnected.

The lecture begins with the well-known case of Lin Shu (林紓, 1852–1924), a celebrated translator of Western literature in late Qing China who did not read any foreign languages. Lin Shu relied on collaborators who orally interpreted foreign texts for him, often based on existing translations. While this process is mostly described as collaborative translation, it was also frequently indirect. Research has shown, for example, that Lin Shu's version of *Don Quixote* drew on two English translations as intermediary sources (Relinque 2022). These mediations were rarely acknowledged: collaborators remained largely invisible and the use of intermediate versions in other languages was not declared.

The lecture then moves to contemporary examples, including the phenomenon of "hidden indirect translations" of Chinese literature in Spain—translations that appear to be produced directly from Chinese but in fact rely on intermediary published translations in other languages (Marin-Lacarta 2018). In contrast, recent decades have seen an increasing expectation that indirect translation be explicitly acknowledged. However, this development is not always linear, and translators of the intermediary texts often remain overlooked. As we will see through examples from different historical and cultural contexts, practices of indirect translation continue to vary, and mediation is not always made visible, revealing ongoing tensions between publishing norms, conceptions of translation and changing ethical expectations.

By examining these and other cases across different historical and cultural contexts, this keynote reflects on what such developments reveal about evolving norms of transparency, authorship, and responsibility in the editorial industry. Indirect translation thus becomes not merely a technical practice but a revealing mirror of broader transformations in translation ethics and in the very conception of translation itself.

References:

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